

An Analysis of Indian Music Aesthetics with Particular Reference to Hindustani Classical Music

Dr. Tanmoy Pal

Assistant Professor, Department of Vocal Music, Rabindra Bharati University
Centre for Distance and Online Education, Salt Lake City, Kolkata, West Bengal

E-mail: tanmoypalmusic@gmail.com

Abstract

Indian classical music is thought to arouse the emotions (Rasas) within. The aesthetics of music have assisted various researchers in discovering its practical use for a healthier living. Both Hindustani ragas have the ability to evoke the rasas. Raga treatment is thought to be useful in alleviating tension, relaxing the mind, and regulating blood flow. Raga treatment has numerous health benefits, as our ancient texts have long stated. This article attempts to demonstrate how the emotions in music have been effectively demonstrated to be a beneficial tool in the treatment of many psychological, neurological, and emotional problems.

Keywords: *Classical, Emotion, Aesthetics, Psychological, Problem, Raga, Rasa. Music, Practical.*

Introduction

Indian classical music has a long history, reaching back to the period of the Vedas, when it was used to recite them. Since then, it has been inextricably linked to human experiences, touching the souls of both the artist and the audience. Shaking the head, clapping the hands in a rhythmic pattern, or tapping the knee to the melody are all involuntary movements triggered by the experience of listening to music and its capacity to touch the soul. It has the ability to reveal concealed emotions. We have seen people listen to their favourite music while working to relieve workplace stress. It is clear that music may be used to enhance our way of life. Melody is a distinguishing quality of Indian classical music, which is recognized through "ragas" in both Hindustani music. The raga is a swara composite arrangement (Seven basic notes in Indian Music). Our book clearly, written many centuries ago, emphasized the link between the Swaras and our bodies. Ragas in the music have the ability to move listeners both physically and emotionally.

State of the Problem

Many students of Indian music, especially those learning Hindustani Classical Music, frequently assume that the aesthetic is created simply by singing or playing the musical notes and the resulting melodies correctly in reference to the technical and grammatical parts of the art form. This issue has caused the learners to engage in two main incorrect practises:

(a) memorising all musical elements that have the potential to produce the "beautiful," which completely disregards individual creativity and innovation.

(b) producing the formal structure of a music, even though it is improvised and grammatically correct but dull, inexpressive, and unappealing.

Questions of Inquiry and Their Goals

This article aims to shed light on the idea that effective music creation and performance depend on a variety of factors, including the individual's creativity and capacity for emotional expression. Both students and professors in many music education institutes have a tendency to overlook this facet of the vast musical legacy. The purpose of this study is to respond to the following queries: What kind of music in the Hindustani musical tradition has the most potential for fostering the "rasa" or aesthetic experience? What possible factors (both required and sufficient factors) could result in the rasa experience in this musical system? What are the requirements for and impediments to the rasa experience in this Hindustani classical music system?

Significance of the investigation

This academic endeavour is crucial because it tends to educate both students and teachers of Indian music about the significance of producing music that is not just grammatically correct but also profoundly aesthetically pleasing and emotionally nourishing. Such knowledge will influence and positively inform teaching and learning tactics and approaches.

Framework for Theories and Conception

This essay discusses the aesthetics of music and how it may be used to convey ideas, rather than only reproducing notes and melodies accurately learned from cramming. A musical performance must be able to "touch their hearts" and elevate them out of the monotony of everyday life in addition to satisfying the intellectual goals of the audience. The Rasa Theory, first put forth by the sage-priest Bharata in his *Natyashastra*, a Sanskrit treatise on drama, and later developed by the rhetorician and Kashmir Shaivite philosopher Abhinav Gupta in his *Abhinav Bharati*, is the theory that is best suited to explain the necessary and sufficient conditions favourable to aesthetic experience of the highest kind. A relevant notion is given if "rasa" is not evoked, as Bharata correctly notes in the sixth chapter of "*Rasadhyaya*". A conceptual framework, as articulated in Indian musicology, underpins this theoretical framework and includes ornamentations, embellishments, improvisation, and emotional expression.

As an Area of Inquiry, Aesthetics

Aesthetics examines what is appealing, captivating, inspiring, fun, and enjoyable in a variety of artistic mediums, including music, painting, theatre, sculpture, literature, and dance. In general, the "beautiful" is perceived through any one, two, or more of the five senses of perception, depending on the nature of the art forms. In music, the aesthetic, or "rasa," is directly experienced through, first and foremost, the sense of hearing and, at most, the sense of sight, in a detached, thoughtful manner.

Music and dance from India (Bhartiya Sangita)

The arts of singing, playing instruments, and dancing—commonly referred to as "Sangita"—are regarded as the foundational elements and primary expressions of Indian culture. These artforms are among the living traditions of the Indians and the Indian Diasporas, and they are performed, promoted, and preserved with a great deal of passion and sincerity.

Indian music encompasses a wide, diverse, and rich legacy of light, folk, classical, and semi-classical music that has developed out of the country's various ethnicities and subcultures and their mutual exchange. This article focuses on Hindustani Raga-Sangita, or classical singing based on ragas, as it is known in the northern region of India.

Raga-Sangita is built on three pillars: Raga (Melodic Matrix), Tala (Rhythmic Cycle), and Pada (Lyrics)

"Raga" and "Tala" are two distinct and fundamental elements that Indian music has provided to the world, whether it be South Indian or Carnatic Music or North Indian or Hindustani classical Music. Many musicologists and musicians consider pada, or lyrics, to be extramusical, despite their importance in vocal music.

Raga

Raga, as it is understood in Indian musical tradition, has no exact equivalent in other musical disciplines around the world. The Raga Form distinguishes a natural and spontaneous sound cluster or phrase - usually consisting of 5-7 notes, although even one, two, three, or four notes can have powerful impacts. The crucial point is that this sound comes naturally and intuitively.

- Sounds from nature
- Easy to understand
- Passively susceptible
- Effectiveness that has been demonstrated

Raga is "the soul of our (Indian) musical system" (Srinivasan, 1999). Gautam (1980) says, ". . . Indian music, despite the persistent impact of European music on for the hundred years or more, has yet kept its unique individual personality. That is primarily due to its raga and tala structure". As a result, one may conclude that the Indian raga system is so deeply ingrained in the musical ethos of aficionados that it will definitely withstand the test of time and the onslaught of change, avoiding degradation of its very existence in India and worldwide.

Several classifications have been proposed by both musicians and academics. Raga is frequently characterised as a combination of notes or a collection of notes that can be sung or played. In a nutshell, raga is a melody. A raga is a musical scale. Raga is also defined as a melodic scheme with the ability to colour or satisfy the listener's imagination. All of these definitions are inadequate because they are only half true and unnecessarily simplified.

Raga is defined by Matanga, the author of Brihaddesi, as a distinctive sequence of sounds that is ornamented, beautified, or adorned with swara (note) and varna (order or movement) and is appealing to the listener.

From them, it is clear that a raga is primarily a certain melodic arrangement created from a collection of sounds that are elegantly and methodically performed. A raga is a psycho-material thing, according to Swami Prajnanananda, since it is an objective expression of the subjective sensation of the mind. Expression in this context refers to the "extra" that an artist contributes to and renders in their performance in addition to the preset form, together with the outward manifestation of notes and their requirements, to project their psychological and emotional emotions. Since there can be no expression without individual freedom and creativity, expression entails freedom.

Raga is a "live" form in which the notes, or pieces, are blended into the whole and follow a sequential or before-and-after order. The notes of a scale are related to one another as higher or lower and are placed in a specific order. Additionally, two particular notes from the group must be in agreement with one another (known as samvada) and are given increased emphasis, resulting in the raga's inner oneness. A raga has an inner pulse since it is made up of ascending and descending note sequences. A raga can be thought of as a

living form with movement and coordination between its elements because of the latter, sharing some characteristics with life.

Tala

Tala or Talam is the other edifice that supports Indian music in general. Tala is a rhythmic cycle that serves as the foundation or basis for a song, instrumental work, or dance. Tala-s are made up of beats, just like raga-s are made up of notes. Tala is used to demonstrate time in music because it is the latter's temporal metre. Tala is thus a unique rhythmic arrangement of beats used to keep time in music in a cyclic fashion.

Each cycle is complete in and of itself and is repeated. A tala might have portions with an equal or uneven number of beats. Each tala in Hindustani Raga-Sangita has its own "Theka," or rhythm signature, which is a group of basic mnemonic syllables that can be used to identify and recognise the tala.

Pada

Apart from raga and tala, the two fundamental principles of Indian music, pada, or literature, or language, is equally important and distinct place in this art form, particularly in vocal music, in all genres, forms, and styles. Pada can be construed as follows:

- (a) metrical or nonmetrical lyrics of vocal music, which are meaningful;
- (b) sets of syllables or mnemonics used to identify strokes of certain musical instruments, or sets of meaningless syllables used in songs (e.g., Tarana and alap of Dhrupada);
- (c) a specific metrical structure with a refrain (e.g., Jayadeva's Gita Govinda).

All three categories are employed in Indian music in general, whereas the first and third categories are used in Khayal and Dhrupada compositions, the two main genres of Hindustani classical music.

A bandish is a skillfully woven composition that combines the essential elements of a raga, the movement and rhythm of a tala, and the significance and linguistic beauty of a text or lyrics. In contrast to "general" poems, the lyrics or pada used in music are written specifically for a raga and tala by a skilled and knowledgeable "musician-poet-composer," known as a vageyakara in old musical treatises. According to Sharangdeva's definition of the latter in his Sangitaratnakara, a composer must not only be a performer but also possess knowledge and proficiency in a variety of fields, including grammar, music theory, aesthetics, languages, rhythmic patterns, and sound employed in poetry. Hindustani vocal or instrumental music often has the set, melodic composition known as bandish. It is performed with rhythmic support from a tabla or pakhawaj, a constant drone, and melodic support from a sarangi, violin, or harmonium. It is set in a certain raga. The components of a composition can be arranged in several ways. The literature component of the music for a standardly structured song is provided by a bandish. In the past, many gharanas used obscenely incomprehensible vocal renditions to prevent their bandishes from leaving the family. It is frequently referred to as cheez in the context of vocal music. A raga is condensed into a bandish. The bandish must capture the essence of the raga in which it is set, whether it does so with words (for khayal) or without (for instruments). That is the key distinction between a bandish and anything like a song. Both are contained inside a melodic framework, although the song's creator is free to use any note that appeals to him aesthetically. A bandish's composer cannot be as intuitive because the raga's grammatical rules must be followed when choosing his set of notes and how they are arranged in relation to one another. However, each raga contains hundreds of bandishes. Each bandish, then, is a reflection of how the artiste understands the raga since most bandishes in the Hindustani tradition are produced by musicians themselves. Two bandishes in the same raga could emphasise various raga elements and produce diverse moods. A bandish is

frequently a sign of musical ancestry because singers from other gharanas would never perform it. Many bandishes take on the mark of particular gharanas.

There are no reason why younger Hindustani musicians can't write bandishes with lyrics that they believe have more literary merit. It's not as though the tradition is devoid of bandishes based on poetry. Indeed, the light classical genres have long embraced Kabir, Surdas, and Tulsidas. Many current khayal singers are also prolific composers; it is obvious to see that their worries are not squabbles with the saas and the nanad. Arati Ankalikar Tikekar performed a bandish in Raga Bhairavi at the Dover Lane Music Conference in Kolkata a few years ago, referring to the essence and structure of Bhairavi itself. That's almost as avant-garde as Paul Auster. Not all endeavours must be as daring, but uninformed listeners may find Hindustani classical music less alienating if there is a sense of a shift toward a different lyric-aesthetic.

Indian Aesthetics

Indian aesthetics is distinctive in that it revolves on and is explicable by the "rasa" philosophy. Indian aesthetics investigates the ability of music or any other kind of art, such as theatre or dance, to communicate, excite, or elicit an emotional state in the performers and to elicit the same condition in the observers, or "rasika-s," as they are known in Sanskrit. According to the belief, this emotional state represented through these arts is known as "rasa.". Indian art developed with a focus on either symbolically representing or producing specific spiritual or philosophical states in the viewer. "Classical Indian architecture, sculpture, painting, literature (kavya), music, and dancing evolved their own rules constrained by their respective media, but they shared with one another not only the fundamental spiritual beliefs of the Indian religio-philosophic mind, but also the processes by which the relationships of the symbol and the spiritual states were worked out in detail," says Kapila Vatsyayan.

The concept of rasa is attributed to Bharata, a sage-priest who lived between the first and third centuries century bc. It was invented by the rhetorician and philosopher Abhinavagupta (about 1000), who used it in all forms of theatre and poetry. According to Bharata, the primary human emotions are delight, laughter, sadness, rage, energy, fear, disgust, heroism, and amazement, all of which might be recast in contemplative form as the various rasas: erotic, comic, pathetic, furious, heroic, awful, odious, magnificent, and quietistic. These rasas are the building blocks of aesthetic experience. The ability to taste rasa is a prize for prior existences' value.

Hindustani classical music's expression and creativity

The whole of our life involves a lot of music. The world over, it is a universal phenomenon that permeates all nations and cultures. Every society has its own distinct view of music, which is dependent on the surroundings, cultures, and lifestyles. The goal of music is to transcend the ordinary and to adorn time, no matter how varied it may be. Music is a universal process that is used to decorate time in every community and culture, similar to how art is used to decorate space.

A raga or melodic composite is defined through singing or playing a musical instrument, while its underlying tonal potentials and distinctive traits are developed and expanded with the aim of triggering emotions in the listeners' thoughts, so preparing the path for the experience of rasa and joy. To do this, two types of music—Nibaddha (bound) and Anibaddha—are performed (unbound). These two ideas signify, respectively, composition and improvisation.

Creativity is an essential part of humanity's efforts for better survival, efficiency at work, luxury and recreation at leisure, diversification, and fulfilment of a natural instinct or fascinating feature of human behaviour. Creativity is a mental challenge. It's all about limitless and eye-catching possibilities. Creativity is the sole reason that humans differ from other species, and it is the driving force behind the evolution and

ascension of the human race. All advancement, whether in technological or social arenas, has been made possible by people's diverse creative aspirations. Artistic creativity connects technology, the business, and society.

It is obvious that the idea of creativity is not limited to one single field, especially art, with which it is most often associated. Similar to how talent can be of varied capacities and also in many professions in any person. Making or designing a finely engineered product or making innovations in both soft and hard goods are both examples of creativity in the engineer's thinking. A broader definition of creativity and creative business includes experiments and inventions in the food industry, fashion design, architecture, computer games, and the film industry, among other industries.

A composition, also known as a bandish, is a tightly knit, structured musical form with text, lyrics, or poetry that is set to a particular melodic form (raga) and rhythmic cycle (tala). Hindustani Raga-Sangita is composed of a huge variety of songs. The main topics of discussion in this article are Khyal and Dhrupada-Dhamar, the two principal classical musical genres. These are two distinct genres in and of themselves, not just musical forms or works. Both are suitable for improvisational raga elaboration and raga delineation. Being creative is a diverse thing. It is a rich source and connected to every area of work and study as a form of self-expression. Here, we're specifically talking about the arts, specifically music. Everyone is aware that music is a discipline that emphasizes experiential learning. An artist's imagination and creativity will be productive if they are given access to the most creative environments possible. Everything depends on the multifaceted experiences that artist has in their lifetime. First, when a child is being raised at home, when the parents try to establish specific experiences in teaching the child to walk, talk, listen, discuss, and observe, creativity is born. The child embraces particular lifestyle norms, educational practices, and behavioral patterns.

Elaboration of a Raga in the Dhrupada-Dhamar Genre

The oldest types of Hindustani classical music that are still popular are Dhrupad and Dhamar. These forms are thought to have their origins in the 'Prabandha' ancient compositional form. The purity of Raga is given particular focus in these forms.

The Dhrupad form is set to Talas like Chau Tala, Sool Tala, Brahma Tala, etc., while the Dhamar form is set to Dhamar Tala. Both forms are sung to the accompaniment of Pakhawaj. While Dhamar's subject matter typically focuses on Holi, Dhrupaad typically glorifies gods and patronizes monarchs. The 16th century, which is regarded as the golden period of these forms, saw the height of both of them.

Dhrupad

The phrases "Dhrupad" and "Dhruvapada," which imply "fixed" and "literary content," respectively, are the roots of the words "Dhrupad" and "Dhruvapada." As a result, Dhrupad can be described as a literary form with verses that are fixed (composed) to specific Svaras and Tala. The themes of Dhrupad's compositions typically include bravery, the honor of praising Gods, Goddesses, and Kings as rulers, as well as melodic elements like Tala and Nada, etc. To the accompaniment of Pakhawaj, this form is sung. ChauTala, Sool, Teevra, Brahma Tala, etc. are some of the "Talas" utilized in Dhrupad.

Dhamar

Dhamar, like Dhrupad, is a compositional form that is performed to the accompaniment of Pakhawaj. Dhamar is always set to the fourteen-beat 'Dhamar' Tala. Dhamar compositions are generally tied to 'Holi' and Leela of Radha-Krishna, but because this genre evolved more in the Medieval period, the compositions also featured themes related to the praise and prestige of Kings and rulers.

Dhrupad and Dhamar have separate rendition styles. The Raga is first performed using mnemonic syllables such as Nom, Tom, Dere, Na, and so on. This part of the song is known as 'Alap,' as it has no rhythmic accompaniment. The Alap builds to a climax of fast rhythmic singing of the mnemonics in the 'Jod' pattern of instrumental music. The composition follows this. The composition is performed with numerous improvisations based on lyrics phrases; this section is called as 'upaj,' and is unique to Dhrupad singing. The improvisations are performed by doubling, tripling, or quadrupling the original tempo before returning to it. Dhamar is likewise depicted in this style. Tala is an essential part of singing Dhrupad - Dhamar.

Elaboration of a Raga in the khayal Genre

In the Indian subcontinent, Khayal is a significant type of Hindustani classical music. Its name originates from a Persian/Arabic word meaning "imagination". Khayal is associated with romantic poetry and gives the artist more leeway than dhrupad. Ragas in khayal are heavily embellished, and the style requires more musical prowess than intellectual integrity.

An artist's natural tendency is to try new things. Both our music and our culture have been impacted by other cultures. During this time of transition, Dhrupad emerged from Prabandh, and the Khayal was created from Dhrupad. Thus, Khayal can be considered a modified version of its two predecessors.

Khayal has three primary characteristics: the use of numerous musical resources, the choosing of various styles of improvisation, and the placement of varied materials to generate a balanced and visually beautiful performance.

Raga is a melodic framework for improvisation based on the premise that specific note patterns (swara) elicit heightened emotional states. These note patterns are a combination of scalar and melodic elements, and each raga may be described in terms of its ascending and descending lines (aroha and avaroha), as well as its distinctive melodic figures in which certain intervals are emphasized and focus is on specific notes. Khayal can be played in hundreds of ragas, with little conceptual constraints in terms of choosing. Instead, such judgments are chosen based on artistic preference, vocal quality, composition type, and time of day of performance. Some khayal singers keep a vast anthology of ragas, while others prefer to focus on a narrower selection. Ragas in the upper register are frequently preferred by persons with high pitched voices, whereas ragas in the lower register are preferred by those with heavier vocal qualities. Similarly, musicians who are skilled in intonation can cultivate ragas with melodic skips, while those who love intellectual and musical challenges may choose complex ragas.

The entire topic of musical meter in Indian classical music is covered by the term tala, which is likely best translated as "time measure." The metrical framework, or beats-based structure, known as a tala is used to create and perform musical works. Different tempos, including slow (vilambita), medium (madhya), and fast, can be used to perform them (druta). The seven talas of khayal—Tilwada, Jhumra, Rupak, Ektal, Jhamptal, Tintal, and Adacautal—are typically used for performance. Although there aren't many composers that employ tilwada, vilambit performance typically uses Jhumra, Rupak, and these three instruments. Ektal is now also used for drut performances, but it was traditionally utilized for vilambit and madhya performances. Performances of the madhya are held in Jhaptal. Adacautal is a drug that is occasionally used for both sluggish and quick performances. Tintal was typically connected to drut performances, particularly those that place a focus on rhythmic play. Various types of embellishment, including swara alap, akar alap, and bol-alap; swara behelava and bol behelava; and swar tana, akar tana, and bol-tana, are sung within the composition for distinguishing the raga once the raga and the composition have been introduced. These are expressed through the wordings of the composition and numerous tonal graces (swara-s) in the musical notes (gamaka-s).

Rasa Experience and Hindustani classical music

Rasa implies sap, juice, or essence in its literal sense. However, it definitely has a distinct meaning when used in connection with the arts, particularly music. Examining aesthetics and the definition of beauty in relation to Hindustani music is the main idea. There are two main components that are required for any such performance. They are the artist's creative process (a musician) and the listeners' aesthetic reaction (a connoisseur). Rasa is a concept that denotes both the artistic and aesthetic processes in Hindustani classical music. Every time a Hindustani musician performs, the audience members recreate what they hear. A rhythmic pattern of sensual and energetic ideas is how the musician conveys his or her emotions. The musician transforms their experience into a musical pattern of sensual and vivacious pictures, which the listener then interprets into a gratifying and pleasurable experience. The musician's creative process cannot take place unless he or she is personally infused with Raga and has the ability to incorporate that into his or her work. The three fundamental elements of Hindustani vocal music, namely Raga, Tala, and Bandish, produce the musician's creative experience, which creates the genre's intrinsic quality. These elements are of utmost significance. The listener's aesthetic experience is the other sense of Rasa. The concept of Rasa stays unfulfilled until the listener recreates the music, and unless the musician's work is properly appreciated by the connoisseurs. Together, they produce Rasa as a whole. Rasa is therefore referred to as the spirit of Hindustani classical music. Since it dominates every Hindustani classical music performance, it is regarded as the genre's foundational music.

Emotional Expression in Hindustani Classical Music

Hindustani classical music, an old genre of Indian music, was created through the fusion of Persian and Vedic musical traditions. Ragas, characterized as musical compositions that can evoke particular feelings or emotions, serve as the foundation of this musical system. Different ragas elicit different emotions. An innovative aspect of raga stimuli is their use of various presentation modes, which vary in tempo/rhythm but are similar in tonal structure, to study music and emotion. They discovered that when the same raga was given in various presentation styles, participants reported evoked emotions and varied arousal.

Both the emotions and the head must be satisfied by music as an art form. One is even inclined to argue that music transcends the knower-known dichotomy when it touches the heart because it takes over the entire being and leaves very little room for intellectual realization.

It is an emotional and spiritual journey from the heart to the mind. For music to have such an emotional effect on a listener, it must be made into a suitable medium for sharing inner emotions and be completely expressive in nature.

Conclusion

Indian classical music has a lengthy history that dates back to the time when the Vedas were being recited, at which point it was used to chant them. Since then, it has been inextricably linked to human experiences and has affected both the public and the artist's souls.

The issues of emotional content, worth, and beauty are issuing that music is unquestionably concerned with. The ability to change or modify feelings and emotions is one of the most wonderful arts that humanity has developed. It is so effective in all living things that it outperforms all forms of treatment. It is the simplest, cheapest, and most straightforward type of treatment for treating many ailments and sufferings experienced by living things in this world. A song, a few chords played on the piano, or performing any instrument will drastically alter the mood. Both the performer and the audience are affected by the influence.

References:

- Kashalkar, Vikas. Aesthetics of Music. Web. 2014.
- Lavezzoli, Peter. The Dawn of Indian Music in the West. Bloomsbury Academic. 2006
- Misra, Shveeta., Shastri, Ina. “Aesthetically Inclined Indian Classical Music”. Journal of Multidisciplinary Engineering Science and Technology. Volume 2. Issue 5. 201
- Bourriaud, N. (1998). Relational form. In *Relational aesthetics*. Retrieved from http://www.kimcohen.com/seth_texts/artmusictheorytexts/Bourriaud%20Relational%20Aesthetics.pdf
- Chaudhary, S. (1986). Contemporary studies in the textual aspect of Dhrupad songs: A summary of selected works. Dhrupad Annual, 1986.
- Mahajan, A. (1989). Ragas in Indian classical music. New Delhi, India: Gian Publishing.
- Saxena, S. K. (1981). Aesthetical essays: Studies in aesthetic theory. Hindustani music and Kathak dance. New Delhi, India: Chanakya Publications.
- Varma, R. (2009). *Indian music: Gateway to salvation*. New Delhi, India: Sasta Sahitya Mandal.
- Sanyal, R. (1987). Philosophy of music. Mumbai, India: Somaiya Publications.
- Shankar, R. (2011). *On appreciation of Indian classical music*. Retrieved from <http://www.ravishankar.org/-music.html>.